

Nurturing Green Mindsets: Investigating Organizational Support in Human Resource Management for Environmental Behavior Enhancement

Amer Sohail

Department of Commerce, University of the Punjab, Gujranwala, Pakistan

Ali Haider Sultan

Department of Commerce, University of the Punjab, Gujranwala, Pakistan

Adnan Ashraf

Department of Business Administration, University of the Punjab, Gujranwala, Pakistan

Usama Ilyas

Department of Commerce, University of the Punjab, Gujranwala, Pakistan

ABSTRACT: This study investigates the mediation effect of green perceived organizational support on the relationship between green human resource management practices and employee environmental behavior in small and medium-sized enterprises in Pakistan. Data from 373 top management personnel were collected through questionnaires and analysed using structural equation modeling with SPSS and AMOS. The results demonstrate that green human resource management practices significantly influence in-role green behavior, extra-role green behavior, green innovative work behavior, and green knowledge-sharing behavior. Importantly, green perceived organizational support emerged as a significant mediator between green human resource management practices and the dimensions of employee environmental behavior. These findings highlight the pivotal role of organizational support in shaping environmentally conscious workplaces and fostering pro-environmental behaviors among employees in small and medium-sized enterprises. This study contributes to the understanding of the mechanisms through which green human resource management practices can effectively promote sustainability initiatives within organizations, providing valuable insights for the development of human resource management strategies tailored to enhance ecological stewardship and promote sustainable business practices. Such insights are critical for advancing sustainability agendas and driving positive environmental changes within and beyond the small and medium-sized enterprises sector.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management, In-role Green Behavior, Green Knowledge Sharing Behavior, Green Innovative Work Behavior, Extra-role Green Behavior.

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1. Introduction

Currently, a major concern is climate change, which intensely affects humans. According to IPCC, from 1980 to 2012, there was an increase in temperature to 0.85°C, which unfavourably affected the grain yields and resulted in a 5% decrease per rise of 1°C. Moreover, as World Health Organization reported its estimated casualties that were 4.3

million, with 2–4 billion USD in economic loss annually because of carbon emissions and global warming. In 2019, the UN prioritized climate change in these alarming figures. However, for an increase in toxic material disposal and carbon emissions, prior studies held other organizations to be responsible. The evolution of traditional business practices over the last few decades is evident, resulting in a shift towards prioritization of the environment to handle these challenges of the environment. Businesses are ascertaining the requirements of environmental responsibility and have adopted policies that focus on sustainable initiatives, such as Green Human Resource Management (GHRM).

GHRM seems to be a strategic method, applying strategies of human resource management in the structures of organizations that are eco-friendly (Ahmed, 2019). This involves policies integrated into environmental practices to promote relationships between businesses and nature. According to Abdul-Rahaman et al. (2021), along with the alignment of ecological sustainability goals, GHRM encourages responsible resource management, waste reduction, and efficient energy usage, which has been emphasized by other scholars (Abdul-Rahaman et al., 2021; Bauhr & Grimes, 2017; Wang & Zhi, 2016). GHRM advocates the integration of eco-friendly practices into its fundamental processes, playing a pivotal role in achieving these objectives (Li et al., 2021). By identifying that the recruitment practices of the HR department directly affect the company's ability to accomplish its goals of environmental management, GHRM serves as a foundation to develop sustainable and environmental workplaces where environmental results are attained with the contributions of employees (Ali et al., 2023; Ali et al., 2022; Xing & Kolstad, 2002).

Furthermore, Green Perceived Organizational Support (GPOS) plays a crucial role in cultivating and nurturing environmentally responsible behavior among employees (Bhatti et al., 2022). GPOS refers to the perception held by employees regarding the extent to which their organization values and supports environmentally friendly practices and initiatives (Karatepe et al., 2022). This perception encompasses not only formal policies and procedures, but also the overall organizational culture and climate pertaining to environmental sustainability (Hameed et al., 2022). Organizational support can manifest in various forms, including the provision of resources for eco-friendly initiatives, the integration of environmental considerations into decision-making processes, the fostering of a culture of environmental responsibility, and the recognition and rewarding of environmentally friendly behaviors (Paillé et al., 2023). The GPOS reflects employees' perceptions of the organization's commitment to environmental sustainability and their belief that their environmental efforts are valued and supported.

Jackson et al. (2012) described attention to employees' behaviors aimed at promoting environmental sustainability, commonly referred to as "employee green behavior." Employee engagement is pivotal for the adoption of green practices, providing a competitive advantage and enhancing the effectiveness of environmental management, as emphasized by (Mazzi et al., 2016). While the existing literature predominantly focuses on large organizations, there remains a gap concerning Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), despite their substantial environmental impact resulting from commercial activities. Nonetheless, stakeholder pressure compels SME management to implement green initiatives (Huo et al., 2022). Recognizing the significance of green employee outcomes, this

study underscores their pivotal role in the successful implementation of environmental management systems.

While previous research has examined the relationship between GHRM and employee green behaviors, less attention has been paid to the mediating role of GPOS in this relationship. This study evaluates the impact of GHRM on In-Role Green Behavior (IRGB), Extra-Role Green Behavior (ERGB), Green Innovative Work Behavior (GIWB), and Green Knowledge Sharing Behavior (GKSB), with GPOS serving as a mediator. The specific focus on mediation enhances our understanding of the mechanisms through which employee behaviors are influenced by GHRM. The theoretical and practical contributions of this study are rooted in its exploration of the relationship between GHRM, employee green behavior, and the mediating effect of GPOS. By illuminating this critical aspect, this study aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers and academia, fostering a deeper understanding of the promotion of eco-friendly behaviors through GHRM initiatives.

The paper begins with an introduction highlighting the significance of climate change, followed by an extensive literature review. Subsequently, the methodology employed in this study is comprehensively demonstrated, and the results and their implications are thoroughly discussed, culminating in a summary in the concluding section.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

GHRM is well-established in the existing studies, as many scholars like Pham et al. (2019) defined it, and also discussed by Tang et al. (2018). GHRM encompasses green training for improvement in skills, hiring employees with environmental knowledge, awareness, competencies, and green performance appraisal based on established standards, and green rewards as a result of their successful application of the organization's green aims. Employee pro-environmental behaviors include in-role behavior, vital for the assessment of official employee performance, and extra-role behavior, which is voluntary engagements that extend beyond the formal job responsibilities that are not part of the assessment of performance (Paillé & Boiral, 2013; Usama et al., 2024).

Empirical research consistently suggests a positive connection between GHRM and various dimensions of employee green behavior. Studies by Chaudhary (2019), Hameed et al. (2020), Dumont et al. (2017), Luu (2017), Fawehinmi et al. (2020) showed a connection between GHRM and employees' green task behavior. According to Social Exchange Theory (SET), the norm of reciprocity for the association of GHRM and green behaviors of employees, including voluntary and task-related activities, is a reasonable description (Blau (2017). Organizations show their commitment to practices in an environment with the help of strong green objectives, rewarding systems, effective training, and performance appraisal, which results in employees' green behaviors.

For organizational competitiveness, Innovative work behavior is important, including the development of ideas, promotion, and realization (Scott & Bruce, 1994). Identified as an essential aspect of attaining a competitive edge Bos-Nehles and Veenendaal (2019), Scholars like Bos-Nehles and Veenendaal (2019) assert that HRM impacts innovative work behaviour, which was also confirmed by (Seeck & Diehl, 2017; Zhou et al., 2013). When

implemented in environmental management, GIWB arises as employees' dedication to developing, promoting, and realizing eco-friendly ideas. The significant influence of GHRM on GIWB was evident in this study. Renwick et al. (2013) discussed how employees with a broader understanding of the environment develop innovative ideas for green innovation. Furthermore, green training helps develop skills, increasing the ability of employees to be involved in innovation (Chen & Chang, 2013; Ilyas, Sohail, Ashraf, & Sultan, 2024). Moreover, Renwick et al. (2013) asserted that green performance evaluation and incentives result in the alignment of employees' behaviors with environmental goals, increasing commitment to the environment. Aligning with SET, the commitment of the organization is reciprocated by the employee towards environmental management with different practices, such as GIWB (McClellan & Collins, 2011; Wright & Nishii, 2007). Research highlighting the positive link between GHRM and GIWB in the context of organizations further supports the concept that employees' perceptions regarding GHRM considerably develop GIWB (Song et al., 2021).

Moreover, studies have considered its importance (Dezi et al., 2019), though the particular influence on organizations is still an area, that is not explored much. The main perspective is that a major role is played by knowledge management to impact several performance consequences, such as better quality of service and customer relationships (Tseng, 2016), and performance of innovation (Bhatti et al., 2021). Within this context, knowledge sharing appears to be a basic domain of knowledge management, analyzed at both the Rubel et al. (2021) and organizational levels (Ferraris et al., 2017; Vrontis & Christofi, 2021). At the individual level, employees benefit the organization through knowledge sharing, resulting in the generation of collaborative knowledge (Teh & Yong, 2011). This collaborative knowledge consists of the knowledge of human cognition and information in the papers. For organizations Knowledge, along with its circulation, is identified as a critical aspect for organizations to achieve competitiveness with sustainability (Gopee, 2015).

Within the wide domain of knowledge sharing, Lin and Chen (2017) outline the GKSB as the level at which environmentally related information is shared by knowledge workers with their colleagues. Consequently, GKSB is conceptualized as the process of spreading information regarding environmental issues between employees to improve the sustainable goals of the organization. (Lin & Chen, 2017) introduced effective green knowledge management, suggesting a better infrastructure of knowledge along with transmission skills within the context of organizations by considering environmental concerns. Thus, the literature suggests that green knowledge sharing is vital to fostering collective understanding and commitment to sustainable practices among organizational members. Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis was proposed:

- H1. GHRM positively influences the IRGB.
- H2. GHRM positively influences the ERGB.
- H3. GHRM positively influences the GIWB.
- H4. GHRM positively influences the GKSB.

According to Shen et al. (2018), is to work according to the community's interests, showing a commitment to environmental protection. However, the GHRM's effectiveness is depending on how organizations address their employees' desires, as highlighted by (Yang et al., 2021). GHRM consists of policies developed to motivate employees to be keenly involved in environmental pollution reduction and upper administration concerns to provide preferences for eco-friendly methods. GHRM was positively correlated with GPOS. The GPOS, as defined by Lamm et al. (2015) and Pinzone et al. (2019), shows the perceptions of employees regarding how organizations give value to their participation in the sustainability of the environment and shows concerns about their beliefs in the organization's environment. Drawing on the perspective of (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002), who highlighted the impact of favourable situations such as rewards, pay, promotion, and development of skills on employees' perceptions of organizational support, Mayes et al. (2017) highlighted the role to improve POS in employees by discussing the significance of their contributions.

Building on the literature on organizational support, AMO theory proposes that employees think that GHRM is an investment to improve their abilities, knowledge, and expertise devoted to safeguarding the environment. (Allen et al., 2003) found that HRM shows the investment of the organization in its employees by providing more awareness towards the support of the organization in actions related to environmental protection, consequently enhancing GPOS among employees. The research meta-analysis carried out by Kurtessis et al. (2017) further supports this perspective, suggesting that improving employees' perceptions of organizational support predicts that the organization will offer support when required in the future. The hypothesis theorized that GHRM practices positively influence GPOS, emphasizing the crucial role that GHRM plays in determining the opinions of employees regarding an organization's focus on sustainability. Hence, the following hypothesis emerges from this perspective:

H5. GHRM positively influences GPOS.

The GPOS has been widely studied, disclosing its positive impact on several employee outcomes. For example, in a study concentrating on hotel employees in Cameroon, Karatepe (2012) found that POS positively impacts career satisfaction. Similarly, Akgunduz and Sanli (2017) confirmed that POS considerably affects job embeddedness among employees in hotels in Turkey. According to the norm of reciprocity introduced in SET, this accomplishment encourages employees to reciprocate via satisfactory work-related outcomes that are related to work (Eisenberger et al., 1986).

This knowledge is integrated to develop an association between the GPOS and employees' green behaviors, and a related principle of reciprocity is noticed here. The employees feel a trusting connection after perceiving that their participation is acknowledged by their organizations, which serve the environment, encouraging engagement in IRGB and ERGB. Empirical findings support this notion; as Aboramadan (2022) states, GPOS positively impacts green helping behavior, green voice behavior, and GKSB. Aboramadan and Karatepe (2021) further explore these findings by illuminating a positive influence between GPOS and non-green behavioral outcomes such as organizational citizenship behavior and job performance among employees in Palestinian

hotels. Building upon these arguments and empirical evidence, it is considered that the GPOS is effective for employees' green outcomes. The faith that environmental contributions are valued by their organizations not only establishes a relationship with trust but also serves as a facilitator for employees to actively participate in green practices, thereby contributing to a positive environmental impact within the organizational context. The following hypothesis was proposed:

H6. GPOS positively influences the IRGB.

H7. GPOS positively influences the ERGB.

H8. GPOS positively influences the GIWB.

H9. GPOS positively influences the GKSB.

Organizations implementing green practices encompass GHRM practices, contributing to positive opinions among employees regarding organizational support for environmental practices. This association is validated by empirical findings showing a causal association among environment-friendly training and development, support of supervisors for eco-friendly initiatives, compensation systems for environmental initiatives, and POS for eco-friendly behavior (Cantor et al., 2012). The accomplishment of environmental initiatives depends on the commitment of top management, involvement of leaders, organizational support, and HR practices that encourage innovation and creativity (Ilyas, Sohail, Ashraf, Siddiqui, et al., 2024; Sugita & Takahashi, 2015). GHRM is helpful in improving employee awareness and commitment to environmental management.

The association between work-related behaviors and employees' attitudes and perceived organizational support is developed in previous studies (Chew & Wong, 2008). This leads to job-related behaviors such as enhanced performance, as an expression of GPOS behaving as a socioemotional source (Burnett et al., 2015). GHRM develops employees' opinions that the organization prioritizes environmental practices and contributes to a positive environment for reciprocity. Environmental training and development further aid in the successful employment of programs that focus on the environment, as evidenced by their positive impact on POS (Cantor et al., 2012).

The theoretical basis of employee reactions can be found in SET, in which organizational support leads to the law of reciprocity. The positive commitment of the organization encourages employees to reciprocate by concentrating on organizational objectives, thereby improving their performance. Empirical findings by Li et al. (2019) confirm the causal relationship of GPOS and behaviours. According to Bhatti et al. (2022) GPOS for practices in the context of the environment serves as a connection between GHRM and environmental results for organizations that are positive. The impact of GHRM is directed towards enhanced performance through the mediating role of the GPOS in environmental activities. (Bhatti et al., 2022) discussed that GPOS is a crucial determinant impacting the results of GHRM into considerable environmental outcomes, developing a pathway for gaining knowledge regarding employees' perceptions. The proposed hypotheses are as follows:

H10. GPOS partially mediates the relationship among.

- a) GHRM and IRGB.
- b) GHRM and ERGB.
- c) GHRM and GIWB.
- d) GHRM and GKSB.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of this study:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

3. Materials and Methods

The research design employed was survey-based to collect data from personnel of top management, such as CEOs, managers, and directors, in manufacturing SMEs situated in Punjab, Pakistan. The Punjab Board of Investment and Trade found that SMEs manufacturing is 65% in Punjab; this region was chosen as per study (Rehman et al., 2021). Manufacturing SMEs were targeted because of their substantial contribution to GDP, employment, and exports, along with their notable environmental impact. Recognizing the government's efforts to improve environmental performance in this sector, we distributed 700 questionnaires through visits and emails. Each questionnaire consisted of comprehensive cover letters attached to it, stating the primary research objectives, and emphasizing strict confidentiality measures in place to safeguard respondents' personal information.

Simple random sampling was employed to choose respondents based on SMEs' names in the SMEDA database. This shows that there are 7859 SMEs in Pakistan, and the sample size was decided using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table showing a minimum sample size of 370 for this population. A total of 419 questionnaires were obtained, of which 373 were considered valid and complete after excluding 46 because of missing values exceeding 25%. The response rate was 53%. The demographic profiles of the respondents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographical Profile

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	245	65.7
Female	128	34.3
Total	373	100.0
Marital Status	Frequency	Percent (%)
Married	236	63.3
Unmarried	137	36.7
Total	373	100.0
Respondent's Education	Frequency	Percent (%)
14 Years	6	1.7
16 Years	92	26.1
M.Phil.	235	66.8
PHD	19	5.4
Total	373	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
Less than 26	81	21.7
26-35	78	20.9
36-45	144	38.6
46-55	63	16.9
56 & above	7	1.9
Total	373	100.0
Work Experience	Frequency	Percent (%)
less than 1	79	21.2
1-5	170	45.6
5-10	72	19.3
15-20	42	11.3
20-25	7	1.09
25 & above	3	0.08
Total	373	100.0

Statistical Strategy

The examination consisted of descriptive statistics, measures' reliability, and correlations, all of which were evaluated using SPSS. However, for hypothesis analysis, AMOS was used for structural equation modeling (SEM), as discussed by (Hair et al., 2018). In particular, PLS-SEM is considered an important technique of multivariate analysis, which is widely used by researchers in several areas, including HRM (Ringle et al., 2020). The PLS-SEM versatility is seen in its use in other fields as well, such as finance (Rai et al., 2019), organizational behavior (Purwanto, 2023), and marketing (Purwanto, 2023). Furthermore, PLS-SEM has the capability to handle measurement errors that are correlated Rademaker et al. (2019) ordinal measures add to its strength in the field of research which is diverse, which was also discussed by (Schuberth et al. (2018).

Measures

The GHRM Dumont et al., (2017) scale, which has six items, was introduced to measure employees' perceptions of GHRM within their organizations, with a high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.959$). For IRGB, the scale developed by Bissing-Olson et al. (2013) was utilized, which has a 3-item scale, that measures formal tasks that are significant for the evaluation of employee performance ($\alpha = 0.881$). ERGB, which encompasses voluntary green behavior, was also evaluated using the instrument developed by Bissing-Olson et al.

(2013) which contains three items representing internal consistency, which is satisfactory ($\alpha = 0.911$).

GIWB was evaluated by adopting the 6-item scale developed by Scott and Bruce (1994) and further adapted by (Aboramadan, 2022), by adding terms that are green-related in accordance with the aim of the research ($\alpha = 0.948$). The GKSB ($\alpha = 0.841$) was measured using a scale containing five items utilized by (Rubel et al., 2021), first established by (Wong, 2013). The GPOS was analysed using a scale with four items ($\alpha = 0.908$) introduced by Eisenberger et al. (1986), a measure previously used by Pinzone et al. (2019) and Hameed et al. (2022) in their studies.

4. Empirical Results

To examine the normality of the dataset, the skewness and mean values were calculated. Table 2 presents each variable.

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis and Discriminant Validity

	Mean	Skewness	IRGB	GHRM	GKSB	ERGB	GIWB	GPOS
IRGB	3.527	-.401	0.846					
GHRM	3.451	-.602	0.616	0.900				
GKSB	3.563	-.590	0.683	0.633	0.856			
ERGB	3.470	-.420	0.706	0.667	0.780	0.882		
GIWB	3.391	-.510	0.691	0.671	0.699	0.686	0.879	
GPOS	3.314	-.388	0.718	0.591	0.744	0.705	0.684	0.846

The mean value for each variable fall within the 1-5 range, which is acceptable and presents the rating scales used in this study for the purpose of measurement. The skewness value is between -1 and +1, which shows that there is a reasonable and symmetric distribution of data. Hence, the validity of the dataset was supported by these results. Every variable has a strong correlation with itself, and underscores that the measures for each construct are distinctive and valid. This study computed CR, AVE, and MSV to rigorously analyze reliability and convergent validity, as shown in Table 3. The reliability of variables such as GHRM, GPOS, IRGB, ERGB, GIWB, and GKS was confirmed with Cronbach's alpha and CR, which was >0.7 .

Table 3. Factor Loading and Convergent Validity

Items	Rotated component matrix						Reliability and Validity			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	Alpha	CR	AVE	MSV
GHRM1	.798						0.959	0.962	0.810	0.450
GHRM2	.815									
GHRM3	.790									
GHRM4	.837									
GHRM5	.790									
GHRM6	.829									
GPOS1				.707			0.908	0.909	0.715	0.554
GPOS2				.730						
GPOS3				.769						
GPOS4				.735						
IRGB1					.702		0.881	0.883	0.715	0.516
IRGB2					.780					
IRGB3					.746					
ERGB1						.705	0.911	0.913	0.778	0.608
ERGB2						.643				
ERGB3						.764				
GIWB1		.766					0.950	0.953	0.772	0.489
GIWB2		.784								
GIWB3		.753								
GIWB4		.746								
GIWB5		.769								
GIWB6		.718								
GKSB1			.743				0.928	0.932	0.732	0.608
GKSB2			.749							
GKSB3			.742							
GKSB4			.731							
GKSB5			.678							

As evidenced by the results, a favourable fit is attained by the model proposed in this study because it fulfils the established criteria. The ratio of CMIN/DF is 2.989, which shows that it is <3, which is acceptable according to the threshold value, that is, ≤ 3 . The GFI is 0.852, which shows that it is greater than 0.80 as per the acceptable range. Similarly, the IFI and CFI were 0.943 and fell within the acceptable criterion of ≥ 0.90 . Lastly, RMSEA is 0.073, which is less than the established criteria. All of these parameters confirm the model's fitness by validating that it is appropriate for subsequent analyses.

Table 4. Confirmatory Factors Analysis

CFA Indicators	CMIN/DF	GFI	IFI	CFI	RMSEA
Threshold value	≤ 3	≥ 0.80	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≤ 0.08
Observed value	2.989	.852	.943	.943	.073

The SEM analysis analysed the complex relationships presented in the model, focusing on the mediating role of GPOS within GHRM and diverse employee behaviors

within Manufacturing SMEs. The estimates and significance levels of the paths between GHRM, GPOS, and targeted behaviors were examined to gain insights into the complexities of the model. The direct effects of GHRM on IRGB, ERGB, GIWB, and GKSB were all positive (H1, H2, H3, H4: Estimates = 0.310, 0.407, 0.464, 0.303; $p < 0.001$). This supports the hypothesis that GHRM exerts a direct positive impact on various green employee behaviors. This calls attention to the contributory role of HRM in shaping employees' green-related conduct.

The results confirm the positive influence of GHRM on GPOS (H5: Estimate = 0.569, $p < 0.001$). This supports the hypothesis that GHRM positively contributes to employees' perception of organizational support for environmental initiatives. Critically, this highlights the strategic role that GHRM plays in shaping employees' perceptions regarding the organizational commitment to green initiatives.

Table 5. Structural Equation Modelling

	Effects	Estimate	S. E	P	Decision
H1	GHRM ----> IRGB	.310	.044	0.000	Supported
H2	GHRM ----> ERGB	.407	.044	0.000	Supported
H3	GHRM ----> GIWB	.464	.043	0.000	Supported
H4	GHRM ----> GKSB	.303	.040	0.000	Supported
H5	GHRM ----> GPOS	.569	.043	0.000	Supported
H6	GPOS ----> IRGB	.425	.043	0.000	Supported
H7	GPOS ----> ERGB	.443	.044	0.000	Supported
H8	GPOS ----> GIWB	.391	.042	0.000	Supported
H9	GPOS ----> GKSB	.495	.040	0.000	Supported
Indirect Effects					
H10a	GHRM ----> GPOS ----> IRGB	.253	.030	0.010	Supported
H10b	GHRM ----> GPOS ----> ERGB	.244	.034	0.010	Supported
H10c	GHRM ----> GPOS ----> GIWB	.218	.031	0.010	Supported
H10d	GHRM ----> GPOS ----> GKSB	.293	.029	0.000	Supported

Furthermore, the analysis revealed strong positive effects of GPOS on IRGB, ERGB, GIWB, and GKSB (H6, H7, H8, H9: Estimates = 0.425, 0.443, 0.391, 0.495; $p < 0.001$). This supports the hypothesis that employees' perceptions of organizational support have a substantial impact on fostering various green behaviors within the workplace. This highlights the importance of employees feeling supported in their environmentally friendly initiatives, extending beyond their formal roles.

The analysis of indirect effects further improves our understanding of these relationships. The significant positive indirect effects of GHRM on IRGB through GPOS (H10a: Estimate = 0.253, $p = 0.010$), GHRM on ERGB through GPOS (H10b: Estimate = 0.244, $p = 0.010$), GHRM on GIWB through GPOS (H10c: Estimate = 0.218, $p = 0.010$), and GHRM on GKSB through GPOS (H10d: Estimate = 0.293, $p = 0.010$) emphasize the mediating role of GPOS on GKSB, GIWB, ERGB, and IRGB. These results highlight the

importance of organizational support as a conduit for the positive effects of GHRM on specific employee behaviors.

5. Discussion on Results

The findings of this study show the critical relationship between GHRM, GPOS, and various dimensions of employee green behavior in Manufacturing SMEs. The direct positive influences of GHRM on GIWB, IRGB, and ERGB confirm the vital role of HRM in shaping employees' green behaviors relates to the social cognitive theory (SCT), as proposed by Wong (2013) and with prior studies demonstrating that GHRM positively impacts employee empowerment, green task behavior and job crafting (Chaudhary, 2019; Fawehinmi et al., 2020; Shen & Deng, 2017). These findings strengthen the theoretical fundamentals proven in the literature concerning the positive influence of GHRM on several aspects of green employee behavior. This study verified the positive influence of GHRM on GPOS, aligning with the norm of reciprocity from SET (Blau, 2017). Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) argue that GHRM conveys organizational support, shaping employees' thinking regarding an organization's obligation to environmental sustainability. This validates Hypothesis 5, which emphasizes the strategic role of GHRM in fostering employees' perceptions of organizational commitment to green initiatives.

However, the results underscored the significantly positive effects of GPOS on IRGB, ERGB, and GIWB. These findings align with SET (Eisenberger et al., 1986), suggesting that favourable organizational conditions lead to increased engagement in task-related and other green activities. The study supports these hypotheses and emphasizes the role of POS in fostering an inclusive approach to green behaviors among employees. Furthermore, the association between GKSB and GPOS is supported, which is consistent with the study of Rubel et al. (2021), aligning with the studies of knowledge sharing in the wider domain of knowledge management, which identifies the importance of environmental sharing of knowledge (Lin & Chen, 2017). The examination of indirect effects improves the knowledge of these relationships. The supported positive indirect effects of GHRM on GIWB, GKSB, IRGB, and ERGB through GPOS highlight the mediating role of GPOS in influencing employees' green behavior. These results align with the arguments presented by Bhatti et al. (2021) and underscore the importance of organizational support in the positive effects of GHRM on specific employee behaviors.

6. Conclusions

This study investigates the effective role of GHRM in transforming employees' green behavior in manufacturing SMEs in Pakistan. IRGB, ERGB, GKSB, and GIWB have a positive relationship with GHRM via GPOS. These findings highlight the impact of incorporating environmental considerations in HRM strategies. These implications increase the adoption of green innovation, knowledge sharing, and organizational support. The research provides insights to policymakers to make their actions related to sustainability goals, identifying the essential role of employees in leading organizations towards a more sustainable and green future.

Research Implications

The positive relationship between GHRM and different dimensions of employee green behavior reflects SET, specifically in the norm of reciprocity. This research highlights the theoretical foundation that invests in organizational GIWB through performance such as green training, recruiting, and rewards, and employee cooperation with pro-environmental perspectives and behaviors. The theoretical basis proves that environmental performance affects employees' organizational commitments involved in both IRGB and ERGB. The experimental confirmation strengthens the positive effect of GHRM on IRGB, and ERGB supports these theoretical aspects. Furthermore, theoretical understanding extends the importance of the study by focusing on GHRM interplay to encourage GIWB. These findings underline the consequences of integrating green determinants into GHRM to encourage innovation and creativity related to environmental objectives, thereby providing a theoretical discussion of green workplace innovation. In the area of knowledge management, this study highlights that GKSB is positively associated with GHRM. The understanding of GKSB not only contributes to knowledge sharing awareness but also outlines the importance of including green aspects in knowledge management strategies. Organizations aspiring to improve their sustainable practices should identify the vital role of GHRM in encouraging the circulation of information that relates to environmental circulation between employees, thus promoting a theoretical understanding of GKSB.

From a practical viewpoint, this research provides valuable insights for organizations, particularly Manufacturing SMEs, with the aim of promoting a green and environmentally responsible organizational culture. GHRM positively affects and focuses on the need for organizations to invest in GHRM as a strategic method to improve employees' perceptions of organizational commitment to environmental sustainability. This viewpoint is critical for organizations working towards building a positive cycle in which employees' GPOS is dynamically involved in both IRGB and ERGB. The suggestions related to the GPOS highlight the importance of promoting a supportive organizational environment that values the environmental participation of employees. Organizations should identify that employees who perceive support for their green initiatives reciprocate more with improved commitment to green behaviors, innovative work, and knowledge sharing, thus contributing to a theoretical understanding of the GPOS. Policymakers can implement environmental aspects into HRM policies, and it will take part in making a workforce that is not only environmentally conscious but also dynamically involved in pro-environmental behaviors.

Limitations and Future Research

The limitations of this research are exclusively dependent on data from SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Pakistan, which significantly limits the generalizability of the findings across various sectors. Another limitation of this study is its cross-sectional design. Future research could improve inclusiveness by introducing new variables into the model, adopting a longitudinal approach for a specific understanding of progressive dynamics, and increasing the scope to include various countries. This would contribute to a globally appropriate framework that is stronger for analyzing the complex associations between GHRM and employee green behaviors.

7. References

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